

Implementation of Attributes, Types, Profiles and Registries

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Editors: U. Schwardmann, C. Blanchi, P. Wittenburg

Authors: I. Anders ([0000-0001-7337-3009](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7337-3009)), C. Blanchi ([0000-0003-2277-5176](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2277-5176)), T. Fitschen ([0000-0002-4022-432X](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4022-432X)), M. Hellström ([0000-0002-4154-2610](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4154-2610)), L. Lannom ([0000-0003-1254-7604](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1254-7604)), A. Pfeil ([0000-0001-6575-1022](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6575-1022)), U. Schwardmann ([0000-0001-6337-8674](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6337-8674)), P. Wittenburg ([0000-0003-3538-0106](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3538-0106))

1. Abstract

This document describes the details that are implied by the working draft on typing from an implementation standpoint. It highlights the roles of FDOs, their PIDs, their attributes and services and registries for FDOs, that need to be established and that operate on objects.

2. Status of this document

This document is a Working Draft of a recommendation track document that has been discussed in the FDO TSIG and BIG Working Group and therefore needs to be discussed and endorsed by the FDO Forum as version WD 1.0, i.e., it will be the FDO Steering Committee which will have to finally endorse this document after having followed the FDO process for Working Drafts.

For the FDO Forum internal reviews and the FDO Community commenting phases we will use appropriate shared drives that support dynamic entry of comments. The URLs of these shared drives will be mentioned in the corresponding documents and requests for comments.

3. Acknowledgments

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5. Introduction

The general concept of an FDO consists of three main components:

- the PID system,
- the FDO model that defines the structures and semantics needed to implement machine actionable binding and
- the FDO service that manages the different resources in a distributed landscape of trustworthy and FAIR compliant service providers.

In this document the components of the FDO model layer are described in more detail together with the relations between them that are needed for the implementation.

Metadata and the bit sequence attached to the PID make up the major components of the FDO and the attachment needs to be made by references given by attributes. The bit sequence is the usual reference provided by current PID systems in a generic resolution process. A machine actionable binding for metadata however is only provided by community-specific approaches and there is currently no generic way for machines to operate on any arbitrary metadata, for instance to understand the inner structure of the bit stream. The FDO approach is an attempt to overcome this lack of automation at least for type, reuse and access related metadata by providing a framework with machine actionability by design.

Machine actionability requires complete syntactic explicitness which can be provided for metadata by a model of keys and values, called attributes, where the key itself is a reference to its description that enables the derivation of a syntax. The values have to follow the requirements of the referred syntax. Such syntax descriptions therefore require a generic access mechanism which can be given again by a PID. They need to be machine-readable, so they need to be FDOs themselves. Also they need services which maintain the attribute definitions, called attribute registries.

A machine that operates on an FDO also needs the information on which attributes it can expect and which is additional metadata, all of which comes from a special attribute called profile. Also the syntax of profiles needs to be defined and there must be an agreement on mandatory attributes. Furthermore the profiles themselves are FDOs and need services which are maintained, called profile registries.

This document describes these in more detail, along with other related components and the relations between them. It describes some possible policies regarding these components and gives hints about the responsibilities of governance for these components. It also gives guidelines on how to implement these components without stating explicit technology choices or a particular implementation framework.

Examples of existing implementations of the described components are provided in a paper¹ derived from an earlier version of this document.

6. Components of an FDO Framework

From an implementation standpoint, services for FDOs, their PIDs and their attributes need to be established to enable operations on objects. The dependencies between such services, the objects and their components can be described in the following way.

¹ U.Schwardmann, T.Kalman: How FDO attributes can support machine- and human-readability? - a description along three examples, 2023, <http://dx.doi.org/10.3897/rio.9.e108737>

Such a description however has the disadvantage that different layers like services and objects with components for different concepts are mixed, which makes it difficult to understand conceptual relations and to make extensions to other important components and objects. Also an important and central component of the FDO, the FDO record, is not explicitly described here.

Therefore another view that only describes objects represented in a digital form together with their relations to each other and in some cases with registries, where such objects are stored in, is needed.

6.1. FDO and Metadata

Starting point of and reason for the description of its implementation is the FDO. In the FDO definition document (Base and full technical definitions of a FAIR Digital Object (FDO)) the following description for FDOs are given.

6.1.1. A full technical definition

A FAIR digital object is a unit composed of data that is a sequence of bits, or a set of sequences of bits, each of the sequences has a (typed) structure that is interpretable by one or more computer systems, and having as essential elements an assigned globally unique and persistent identifier (PID), a type definition for the object as a whole and a metadata description (which itself can be another FAIR digital object) of the properties of the object, making the whole findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable both by humans and computers for the reliable interpretation and processing of the data represented by the object.

This description is technology independent and this should also be the case for the description of the concrete implementation of its components.

We start therefore with the more general concept of a digital object (DO) that was already discussed and described in the RDA working group on Foundations and Terminology as lying in the middle of PID, metadata and bit sequence and relating these components to each other. This view is adopted essentially in this diagram with the additional property that a PID is recognized as an FDO of itself.

For FDO this is adopted, however the relation between FDO to metadata and bit sequences is here explicitly given as references provided by attributes as parts of an FDO record, which overcomes the restrictive one to one correspondences in the former diagram. Furthermore, it should be mentioned that neither references to metadata nor to bit sequences are mandatory for FDOs. Examples exist where both, metadata and bit-sequence, are part of the FDO record itself. On the other hand, if such references exist structural information like schemas has to be available, but the targets are not necessarily required to be FDOs again.

In such a view

also schema information for the metadata and bit sequence can be provided, because of its structural similarity with attribute definitions for FDO records. In comparison to the RDA figure above one could easily also add the aspect that aggregations of FDOs like collections are again FDOs, but this aspect of aggregations goes beyond the scope of the implementation details for those components that are in question in this document.

The FDO-Record of the object and its attributes are described in more detail in the following, which discloses a more complex infrastructure with more components and relations.

6.2. FDO-Record and Attribute Definitions

For technology independence reasons we prefer the name FDO record here instead of PID record as it is named in several other documents of the FDO Forum. In this specific view of a possible implementation of the concept of FDOs we want to emphasise the option to not explicitly rely on attributes stored in a PID record, but to also allow other possible storage methods based on other technology decisions.

For the concrete implementation of an FDO record several options are available. If PID systems are capable of storing attributes as key value pairs together with the resolution information into the PID record, for instance in data, FDO records can be realised this way. This is the most straightforward and thus the default way to implement the FDO Record. However, other solutions in repositories can be made available, for instance using links to database records or providing structured landing pages containing this information. Which option is chosen has to be transparent for the machine in any case. How agents detect and understand a non-default option still needs to be described at the present time.

A central property of the FDO record, as of the PID record, is its structure as an aggregation of attributes, which are key value pairs. In the FDO framework a special kind of attribute plays an outstanding role: the type of an object, which is here assumed to be a reference to a description on how a machine can digest the content of the object². Often such type descriptions are currently provided in a human readable form, but it is one of the goals of FDO to also provide type descriptions in a form that machines can read.

The values in the key value pairs of an FDO record comply with the descriptions that are provided for the domains of the keys. This is a universal pattern for the delegation to substructures. For instance XML suggests namespaces to avoid name conflicts, actually they point to substructures for keys or in Linked Data 'contexts' for keys in each object are suggested. In all cases the delegation works via references for keys and the reference describes the value space.

Due to the general principle that FDOs need to be machine actionable this means that the description has to be provided in such a form that machines can at least decide whether the value is in the domain of the key. At best, machines can automatically operate on all aspects of the FDO on the basis of the information provided by the FDO record.

² Typing FDOs: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7825598>

Because of the needed availability and persistence of this information, these descriptions have to be stored in attribute registries as FDOs. Because of the descriptive power that is needed to ensure automated processing of FDOs, the descriptions have to be highly formalised. To emphasise the formalisation of the key descriptions used in attributes we call them attribute definitions. These attribute definitions constrain therefore the values of the attributes.

In order to implement such a formalisation, the way how attributes are defined needs a structural frame beside being an FDO and this is provided as attribute schemas by the FDO Framework, which are again defined as FDOs.

We have described above that the keys of FDO attributes are PIDs. These PIDs reference other FDOs, called “attribute definitions”, that describe what can be expected in an attribute and specify the value space of an FDO attribute. This is the way an implementation is supposed to find the schemata for respective attributes that constrain values, for instance the profile attribute schemata.

Attribute definitions are stored in dedicated services, called “attribute registries” and the FDO record of an attribute definition contains a reference to the attribute definition itself and an attribute with the FDO-Content-Type, the type of the type.

But a machine also needs to find out how to process the type or attribute definition behind the key. Therefore there is also a schema or definition available for type or attribute definition, again defined as FDOs of data objects in an FDO schema repository. For the definition of attribute definitions the same schema can be used as that for attribute definitions itself, or in other words attribute definitions are capable to also describe definitions of attribute definitions. This way all needed types to process values in attributes can be provided and machine actionability is enabled in this model.

6.3. Profiles

On the other hand, also the structure of the FDO record needs to be described in a way such that machines know what they can expect in the record and how to operate on it. This description is

called FDO profile and essentially contains a list of allowed and needed attribute keys for which the FDO record provides values. An FDO record contains as one needed attribute a key for the profile key and the value to this key is the specific FDO profile for the FDO.

For machine actions also for this description a schema, the profile schema or profile definition, has to be given that describes how to read the profile. These profile schemas can be found in a schema repository as part of the FDO framework. To be able to read the profile definition the same schema as for attribute definitions and the definition of attribute definitions can be used. Again the FDO profile and the schema for the profile are FDOs.

6.3.1. Disambiguation of Names for Keys by Profiles

Apart from specifying mandatory and accepted keys of an FDO record, the profile also opens the possibility for semantic enhancements of the FDO by introducing names to the keys. This can be provided in two ways. The names can already be given in the attribute definition as its name and the profile section referring to a key can also contain a naming information. Currently there is no rule, which name has preference, but since the profile is more specific to the FDO in question (an FDO has one profile but the attribute definition can be used in many profiles) it is recommended to use the naming information of the profile in the first place and the attribute name only if there is no name given by the profile. This way an FDO record can be prepared in a more human readable form providing semantics at the same time.

A typical example of such an approach is shown in the chapter ‘The DARIAH Use Case’ in the examples paper³ and the profile for the legacy DARIAH Handle records⁴, where the name in the profile overwrites the names in the original type definition. In the case of the URL key the name in the profile description could have been omitted such that the name of the attribute, again URL, would be chosen.

6.3.2. The FDO Configuration for Profiles

For interoperability there is a need to standardise the FDO profile with respect to a minimal set of attributes that can be found in each FDO record.

³ U.Schwardmann, T.Kalman: How FDO attributes can support machine- and human-readability? - a description along three examples, 2023, <http://dx.doi.org/10.3897/rio.9.e108737>

⁴ Profile for DARIAH Handle records: <http://dtr-test.pidconsortium.eu/#objects/21.T11148/f1eea855587d8b1f66da>

Because the FDO record is the entry point for machines to gain the necessary information to operate on them, the profile is a needed information that has to be provided as an attribute in any case.

Whether this is sufficient or there are other attributes, which are mandatory for an FDO, and which profile provisioning option is chosen, is depending on the use case and the kind of FDO used there. Often an FDO refers to some bit sequence and is described by metadata, but also it could contain just some constant number for instance. Therefore the only mandatory attribute in the FDO Profile is the FDO Profile itself.

Typically, depending on the use case, the set and the arrangement of needed attributes to fulfil the requirements for FDOs can be different. FDO Forum has discovered a couple of different ways, so called configuration types⁵, to provide the necessary information. These FDO configurations build a framework to express the necessity of certain attributes and possible dependencies between attributes. Other aspects for the choice of attributes are covered for instance by genres (s.b.).

Again the attributes given in the FDO configuration can be named, but in order to not hamper the semantic expressibility of community specific naming in profiles, names in the FDO configuration should be clearly expressed as such (e.g. FDO-date for the date format expected by the FDO configuration).

6.3.3. Advanced Policies and Rules for Profiles

As seen with the rules of the FDO configuration but also with the precedence rule for naming it is also possible to implement special policies for the attributes determined in profiles. Other rules, for instance the use of only selected attribute registries, the use of special schemas for attribute definitions or certain additional interoperability requirements are also possible and such rules could be given in a hierarchical manner depending either on the internal definition hierarchy of the attributes or on the hierarchy of the identifier spaces used by the FDOs. In any case, such policies are widely community specific except for the FDO configuration rules which are binding for all FDOs.

In the FDO Forum a working draft for Kernel Attributes and Metadata⁶ is provided. The goal there is to distinguish between mandatory, recommended and optional attributes in FDO records. A possible profile for FDOs is then a definition of attributes that fulfils these requirements. It must contain the mandatory attributes and it can use subsets of the recommended and optional attributes, but it also can go beyond these attributes for special community requirements.

6.3.4. RDA Recommendations for Kernel Information Profiles

In 2018 the RDA PID Kernel Information working group provided a recommendation on Kernel Information Profiles (KIP)⁷ that contains seven guiding principles regarding the attributes used. The idea behind these principles was to foster machine actionable services and to enable high speed decision processes on values in the attributes of PID records. These goals also have some value for the usage of profiles for FDOs.

These principles have been evaluated in the light of the FDO description of the FDO record and of the purposes of FDO records as well as results from the practical use of kernel information. This led to some adaptation of the RDA KIP principles. For FDO records and their profiles we recommend to use the following set of consistent principles that use the FDO glossary and are brought into a new more intuitive order:

⁵ FDO Configuration Types, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7825702>

⁶ FDO Kernel Attributes and Metadata <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7825692>

⁷ RDA Recommendations for Kernel Information Profiles: <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00031>

FDO-KIP-P1 (from RDA-KIP-P1): The primary purpose of an FDO record (PID Kernel Information record) is to serve machine actionable services.

FDO-KIP-P2 (from RDA-KIP-P6): A profile describes the FDO (PID) Kernel Information of an FDO (PID) record. Attributes (items) in the profile are expressed as key-value pairs where the values should be kept simple to avoid long parsing time.

FDO-KIP-P3 (from RDA-KIP-P3): The FDO (PID) Kernel Information is stored directly in the FDO record at the resolving service. If an attribute is used to enable high speed decision processes it should not be referenced to avoid additional redirection.

FDO-KIP-P4 (from RDA-KIP-P4): Change to an FDO (PID KI) record can be only by a data object owner or owner delegate (e.g., FDO (PID) record manager).

FDO-KIP-P5 (from RDA-KIP-P5): FDO (PID KI) record values should change infrequently with updates initiated only by an appropriate authority, avoiding human interaction on updates where possible

FDO-KIP-P6 (from RDA-KIP-P7): Every attribute value in an FDO profile (PID KI profile) depends only on the identified object and no other objects.

FDO-KIP-P7 (from RDA-KIP-P2): If the information for an attribute duplicates metadata that is maintained elsewhere, an automated synchronisation mechanism between these metadata locations has to be implemented.

There is an ongoing discussion with RDA about an update of the original KIP recommendations in the sense of the recommendations above.

6.4. Operations and Profiles

As described above, machine actionability and operations play an important role in the FDO framework, where we understand operations as operations applied on FDOs.

Operations in the context of FDO are a topic of its own with several aspects that go far beyond the scope of this document. However in the view of this document and the implementation of attributes given above we abstract from most of these advanced aspects and describe an operation as a special kind of FDO with an FDO record that may contain a reference to its code, references to services running this code and a full description of needed input and (optional) outcome of the service. This information is completely provided by the attributes of the FDO record of the operation, which is only given implicitly in the following diagram by saying that an operation is an FDO.

The diagram above has an emphasis on the question whether a certain operation can be applied to a certain FDO. This has to be answered completely by the attribute information that is available for the FDO and the operation. In other words this applicability can be described as a match between requirements of the operation for the existence of particular attributes in the FDO record. These requirements have to be described as attributes in the FDO record of the operation. Whether an operation is applicable for a given FDO can be matched directly between their FDO records.

6.4.1. MIME-like Types as special case

Currently operations on digital objects are often chosen according to their so called MIME type. Behind these MIME types are in general purely human readable descriptions that are endorsed and collected by IANA⁸ and that are understood by programmers to develop code for operations on the digital objects with very specific purposes. Since there is no machine actionability between type description and code development, currently no automated generation or adaptation of code is possible, even if MIME types have similar data structures or operations should have similar outcomes. The idea of well defined FDO records targets beside others this lack of automation.

However the MIME type concept has provided a huge amount of proprietary and public domain software operations that are available and can be integrated into the FDO framework by assuming that a MIME type is given as an attribute. Implementations could provide an attribute definition that has the MIME types as its value domain, in other words it allows all names or suffixes of MIME types as values. Or as another option each MIME type instance gets an attribute definition on its own and the MIME type attribute definition has the attribute definitions of the MIME type instances as its value domain. In this case the attribute definitions of the MIME type instances can contain just a name and a URL pointing for instance to the human readable descriptions of IANA.

The MIME type attribute itself contains the MIME type attribute definition as key and the specific MIME type, given as name or attribute reference as value. The structure behind the MIME types is not further disclosed at that level, but machines can use this information to hand over to operations according to the MIME type.

⁸ IANA media types: <https://www.iana.org/assignments/media-types/media-types.xhtml>

The MIME type concept has influenced many community solutions with human readable descriptions of structures of digital objects and self developed operations to handle them. This in most cases was made as '**MIME-like**' types without getting an official MIME type status, which implies an often lengthy endorsement process.

The FDO approach on the other hand provides a framework that enables communities and interest groups to define structures of digital objects in lightweight processes with the additional advantage that automated processes can accelerate operation development.

Nevertheless these 'MIME-like' types with only human readable descriptions and their operations exist. If one however integrates such 'MIME-like' types into the FDO framework in a similar way as MIME types by using an attribute definition with reference to the description as placeholder, one gets the problem that the collection of all the MIME type attribute definitions would be very frequently changing. Here the attribute definition for 'MIME-like' types that requires a name and the reference to the human readable description as key and the name and reference as value would be sufficient.

A MIME type (or MIME-like type) is described as an FDO with metadata specific to this MIME type. This FDO is based on an attribute definition for the metadata schema for MIME types. Then as the key this attribute definition is used and as value the specific FDO of the MIME type of choice. This is described in more detail in section 7.3.

6.5. Genres of FDOs

There is another approach that highlights a special aspect. The attributes in general describe certain properties of the digital object and those properties can belong to the same or different concepts. In the centre of the diagram above is the FDO and many of the relations of components to this central element are of the kind 'is_a', where the FDO type as a subset of an FDO profile has also the 'is_a' relation to FDO. This leads to the following figure.

Since these components are on different levels of abstraction and are used for completely different purposes in the FDO infrastructure, they belong to different concepts. All these components can occur as keys of attributes. In other examples an attribute can describe access rules, another the internal structure and another available data locations. In some cases, depending on the concept, only one value is allowed in others more than one. It is also possible that if a certain attribute is given others become mandatory or forbidden.

In the wording of the FDO framework these different concepts of attribute are called genres with the possibility to have other genres beyond those used here to describe the FDO Framework. In the FDO configuration framework it can also be possible to express the necessity of attributes coming from certain genres and the necessities and dependencies for genres of attributes. The genres are therefore from a processing viewpoint mainly characterised by their attributes and in particular their profile, which determines the set of allowed attributes of an FDO.

Another view of this part of the diagram regarding these ‘is_a’ relations in the first place is to put all components that are FDOs on one level and to describe additional features of them by ‘has’ relations, which leads to the following diagram.

The components of this diagram are only to small parts completely under the control of the FDO Forum on one side or the communities on the other side. Most of the components are diverse, where often the description of the general principles and underlying processes is given by the FDO Forum and the concrete design and application is done by the community. An overview over this governance aspect is given by the following figure.

